

Simulation of GAIA scanning of arbitrary directions

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1 Introduction

The scanning of GAIA across arbitrary points on the sky can be simulated by means of two Fortran programs, `nsl.f` and `scan.f`, which are available by anonymous ftp from `nastol.astro.lu.se` (directory `incoming/lennart/SAG-LL-026-dir`).

The first program (`nsl.f`) generates a list (`nsl_gaia.prn`) of the spin axis positions for a 5-year mission, using uniform revolving scanning with sun-spin axis angle $\xi = 55$ deg. The scanning law is defined by the differential equation (12) in SAG-LL-014+14A with $S = 4.003$.

The second program (`scan.f`) uses the output from `nsl.f` to determine the transits of a given point on the sky across one or several instrument fields. The characteristics of the fields and of the sky position(s) are specified in a configuration file called `scan_in.txt`. Specific positions as well as random positions can be defined. Ecliptic, equatorial or galactic coordinates can be used.

The ftp area contains the two source codes, `nsl.f` and `scan.f`, as well as the output file `nsl_gaia.prn`, a sample configuration file `scan_in.txt`, and the corresponding output files `trn_gal.prn` and `sum_gal.prn`. The file `scan_gaia.prn` is required as input to `scan.f`. To be able to run `scan.f`, the user could either retrieve `nsl_gaia.prn` by ftp, or generate it by means of `nsl.f`. Relations among the files are illustrated in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. Relations among the two programs `nsl.f` and `scan.f` and the various input/output files. The name of the configuration file must be `scan_in.txt` in order to be recognized by `scan.f`. Other file names can be changed as specified in `scan_in.txt`.

2 Scanning law file

The content of the file `nsl_gaia.prn` as generated by `nsl.f` is illustrated by the first ten lines:

```
.000 280.374 .993140 .000 .909045 -.416698 .000000
.125 280.501 .993139 .608 .909924 -.414684 .008699
.250 280.628 .993137 1.218 .910707 -.412686 .017410
.375 280.756 .993136 1.828 .911395 -.410703 .026133
.500 280.883 .993134 2.440 .911986 -.408737 .034867
.625 281.011 .993133 3.052 .912481 -.406788 .043611
.750 281.138 .993132 3.665 .912879 -.404857 .052364
.875 281.266 .993131 4.279 .913181 -.402945 .061125
1.000 281.393 .993130 4.895 .913385 -.401053 .069893
1.125 281.520 .993129 5.511 .913492 -.399180 .078667
```

The columns are: (1) time in days from beginning of year (actually J2000.0 is used as origin); (2) solar longitude in degrees; (3) solar distance in AU; (4) revolving angle ν in degrees; (5–7) ecliptic *xyz* components of the spin axis. The number of lines is 14 611 (end time is 1826.250 days or exactly 5 years after the start time).

Shorter or interrupted missions can be simulated by removing sections or individual lines from the table. Note however, that only time intervals between points separated by (approximately) the spin period (0.125 day) are considered. For instance, if every n th line is removed, then observations are only made during a fraction $(n - 2)/n$ of the time.

3 Configuration file (`scan_in.txt`)

The following version of `scan_in.txt` serves to illustrate the specification of input parameters for `scan.f`:

```
# simulation of GAIA scanning, 29 Dec 1998
# two Astro fields (1,2) and one Spectro field (3) are simulated
nsl_gaia.prn
trn_gal.prn
sum_gal.prn
FIELD 53 -0.33 0.33 1
FIELD -53 -0.33 0.33 1
FIELD 180 -0.50 0.50 0
GAL
40 80
RANDOM 10
```

The file begins with any number of comment lines. Then follows the specification of the scanning law file (`nsl_gaia.prn`) and the two output files (`trn_gal.prn` for transit data and `sum_gal.prn` for summary data). A blank line can be used to indicate no output: e.g. if very many random directions are simulated, one is perhaps only interested in the summary data.

Then follows the definition of fields, in this case the two Astro fields (at angle ± 53 deg from the instrument x axis) and the Spectro field (at angle 180 deg from the x axis). The numbers ± 0.33 deg and ± 0.50 deg are the extents of the fields in the across-scan direction. The last number (1, 1 and 0 for the three fields) is the statistical weights assigned to the astrometric measurements in respective field. Up to 30 different fields can be defined.

The coordinate system is then specified. Valid options are 'ECL', 'EQU' and 'GAL' for ecliptic, equatorial and galactic coordinates. This is the coordinate system used for the subsequent positions, and for the output.

The following lines, right up to the end of the file, define the points on the sky to be scanned. The points can be specified explicitly in spherical coordinates — in the sample file above, the first position is at galactic longitude 40 deg, latitude 80 deg. Alternatively, n random directions can be specified as 'RANDOM n '. The random positions are always the same on the sky (unless the random number seed idum is changed in the program).

4 Transit file

The program scan.f generates two output files: the transit file and the summary file. Their names are specified in the configuration file. The transit file gives one line of output for each transit, i.e. for each passage of the object across the central vertical line of a field. Here are the first 20 lines in trn_gal.prn generated with the configuration file above:

```
# simulation of GAIA scanning, 29 Dec 1998
# two Astro fields (1,2) and one Spectro field (3) are simulated
# coordinate system = GAL
# scanning law from nsl_gaia.prn
#  obj  trn fld   time    z(deg)    zdot  posang    wpar    zpar
    1    1  3  11.60556  -.4171    .1707  236.716  -.7967  -.5698
    1    2  1  11.64977  -.2361    .1706  236.731  -.7962  -.5698
    1    3  2  11.68658  -.0854    .1706  236.745  -.7958  -.5698
    1    4  3  11.73067   .0951    .1706  236.762  -.7953  -.5698
    1    5  1  11.77489   .2760    .1704  236.779  -.7947  -.5698
    1    6  3  38.23705   .4160   -.1526  320.800   .6299  -.5715
    1    7  1  38.28118   .2542   -.1529  320.879   .6308  -.5715
    1    8  2  38.31798   .1191   -.1529  320.946   .6316  -.5715
    1    9  3  38.36208  -.0428   -.1529  321.025   .6325  -.5715
    1   10  1  38.40620  -.2049   -.1532  321.104   .6335  -.5715
    1   11  3  89.46443  -.4527    .0245  199.295  -.0828  -.5788
    1   12  3  89.58966  -.3831    .0226  199.789  -.0757  -.5788
    1   13  3  89.71488  -.3191    .0207  200.283  -.0686  -.5788
    1   14  1  89.75921  -.2975    .0188  200.459  -.0661  -.5788
    1   15  2  89.79601  -.2809    .0188  200.604  -.0640  -.5788
```

The comment lines from scan_in.txt are copied to this output file. Three more comment lines were inserted by scan.f: the coordinate system, the scanning law file, and column headers. Then follows one line per transit, ordered by object and time: (1) object number; (2) transit number; (3) field number (in the order they are defined in scan_in.txt); (4) time of transit in days; (5) across-scan coordinate z in degrees at which the object crosses the central vertical line in the field; (6) the vertical speed in arcsec/s; (7) the position angle of

the scan, in the specified coordinate system (galactic in this case); (8) the parallax factor along scan (i.e. the displacement along the scan is the parallax times this factor); (9) the parallax factor across the scan (this is always close to $-\cos \xi \simeq -0.57$).

5 Summary file

The second output file contains one line per object, as illustrated by the file `sum_gal.prn` generated with the configuration file above:

```
# simulation of GAIA scanning, 29 Dec 1998
# two Astro fields (1,2) and one Spectro field (3) are simulated
# coordinate system = GAL
# (pos1 = gal. longitude; pos2 = gal. latitude)
# scanning law from nsl_gaia.prn
# reference epoch = 913.1250
# obj   pos1   pos2  n_trn   c_1     c_2    c_par   c_pm1   c_pm2
# 1  40.000  80.000  559   .1008   .0822  .1320   .0647   .0527
# 2  30.265  24.197  407   .1151   .0853  .1374   .0929   .0741
# 3 197.712 -10.812  257   .1216   .1173  .1590   .0924   .0989
# 4  66.040 -19.775  403   .1072   .1207  .1476   .0615   .0880
# 5  99.799 -38.642  249   .1235   .1232  .1507   .0799   .0814
# 6  28.623  54.374  434   .1122   .0774  .1290   .0817   .0603
# 7 310.036 -28.838  258   .1191   .1162  .1123   .0827   .0808
# 8 147.363  21.567  332   .1126   .0968  .1219   .0807   .0695
# 9  70.645 -31.041  346   .1057   .1013  .1452   .0867   .0794
#10 229.468  38.543  223   .1238   .1334  .1596   .1045   .0958
#11 275.097  59.339  196   .1401   .1357  .1589   .0956   .0930
```

The comment lines from `scan.in.txt` are copied also to this output file. Five more comment lines were inserted by `scan.f`: the coordinate system, an explanation of the meaning of the spherical coordinates (`pos1` and `pos2`), the scanning law input file, the reference epoch (in days), and column headers. Then follows one line per object, with the following data: (1) object number; (2–3) spherical coordinates in degrees; (4) total number of transits (all fields); (5–6) coefficients of improvement for `pos1` and `pos2` at the reference epoch; (7) coefficient of improvement for the parallax; (8–9) coefficients of improvement for the proper motions in `pos1` and `pos2`. The coefficient of improvement is the ratio of the standard error of an astrometric parameter to the standard error of its one-dimensional (along-scan) position on the sky, as determined from a single transit.

6 Some statistical results

The program `scan.f` was used (with the nominal scanning law in `nsl_gaia.prn`) to determine the transits across Astro-1 and Astro-2 of 5000 random directions on the sky. The number of transits (n) and the coefficients of improvement (C) for the individual directions are shown in Figs. 2–7. The overall mean values are: $n = 168$, $C_\lambda = 0.115$, $C_\beta = 0.118$, $C_\pi = 0.138$, $C_{\mu\lambda} = 0.081$, $C_{\mu\beta} = 0.083$. Note that the simulation does not include the 10 per cent dead time actually foreseen in the mission study.

Figure 2. Number of transits across Astro-1 and Astro-2 for a 5 year mission. Each point is for one of 5000 random directions.

Figure 3. Coefficient of improvement in parallax for the same directions as in Fig. 2.

Figure 4. Coefficient of improvement in ecliptic longitude for the same directions as in Fig. 2.

Figure 5. Coefficient of improvement in ecliptic longitude for the same directions as in Fig. 2.

Figure 6. Coefficient of improvement for the proper motion in ecliptic longitude; directions as in Fig. 2.

Figure 7. Coefficient of improvement for the proper motion in ecliptic latitude; directions as in Fig. 2.